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Informing the decision-making process for potential PMT/vPvM chemicals through the adoption of a risk-based prioritization framework: the ZeroPM approach

Todd Gouin¹ , Annette Bitsch², Majorie van Duursen³, Sylvia E. Escher² and Timo Hamers^{3*}

Abstract

A risk-based strategy is presented aimed at prioritizing chemicals screened as potential persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) or very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances. Prioritization is done to strengthen the decision-making process regarding actions that might be taken against chemicals screened as potential PMT/vPvM substances. Such actions can range from acquiring additional data aimed at reducing uncertainties in toxicological effect concentrations or internal exposure concentrations to—in case of acceptable uncertainty—suggesting compounds for prevention and/or removal measures in order to limit future exposure. The prioritization strategy is developed within the ZeroPM project and applies a variety of tools, including *in silico* and *in vitro* models for exposure and toxicity hazard assessment. These tools will be applied to chemicals identified as PMT/vPvM substances, with a preliminary emphasis on substances belonging to three chemical classes, i.e. perfluorinated compounds, triazines and triazoles. Here we describe the ZeroPM approach providing a proof-of-principle illustrative example, based on data-rich substances, results from which demonstrate how prioritization can be achieved using a risk-based approach that uses data obtained from new approach methodologies (NAMs) and environmental exposure concentrations, obtained either through modelling or monitoring studies. Results are communicated using a risk-based prioritization matrix, which can be used to help to communicate prioritization needs, such as identifying data gaps or for guiding actions aimed at mitigating exposure. The precision and accuracy of the prioritization matrix is evaluated using several data-rich chemicals, which identifies perfluorooctanoic acid and perfluorooctane sulfonic acid as high priority, due to a combination of toxicity and exposure estimates, whereas atrazine and melamine are observed at lower priority. The proposed risk-based prioritization framework thus represents a complementary source of information that should help support regulatory decision-making for PMT/vPvM substances.

Introduction

There has been ongoing interest by regulators and water managers to apply screening and prioritization methods aimed at identifying chemicals used in commerce that may have the potential to contaminate sources of drinking water [1–6]. Most notably are the initiatives that have been progressed in Europe, particularly the German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt—UBA), who have proposed a suite of screening criteria that are meant to identify the properties of chemicals that may represent

*Correspondence:

Timo Hamers
timo.hamers@vu.nl

¹ TG Environmental Research, Sharnbrook, Bedfordshire, UK

² Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine ITEM, Division Chemical Safety and Toxicology, Hannover, Germany

³ Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – A-LIFE Institute for Life and Environment, Amsterdam, Netherlands

a hazard to drinking water [1]. The primary goal of the screening criteria is to identify chemicals that have a combined potential to be persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) or very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) under the EU chemical regulation REACH (EC 1907/2006 Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals) [7] and CLP (EC 1272/2008 Classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures) [8].

Screening and prioritizing chemicals with respect to the properties of persistence, mobility and toxicity implies that these properties are sufficient to result in their ability to reach drinking water sources and that there is an associated 'hazard' that PMT chemicals may eventually exceed a toxicological level of concern and thereby represent a risk to human health [1, 9–12]. Indeed, in a report published by the European Commission, PMT chemicals are identified as representing a threat to water resources that are of *equivalent concern* to persistent hydrophobic organic chemicals that have the potential to bioaccumulate [10]. Under REACH, which aims to ensure a high level of protection of human health and the environment (Article 1.1) and is underpinned by the precautionary principle (Article 1.3), chemicals that fulfil the screening criteria associated with being persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (i.e. PBT) or very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB), can result in their identification as substances of very high concern (SVHC). Following Article 57 of REACH, a classification as SVHC can result in their authorization or restriction of use in Europe, with similar arguments being presented in the case of PMT chemicals [11].

To support the prioritization of chemicals used in commerce that may potentially be identified as PMT, the Horizon 2020 European Union's research and innovation funding programme has provided financial support to the ZeroPM project [6]. One of the goals of the project, therefore, is to develop and apply a suite of tools that can be used to prioritize chemicals screened as PMT substances. Prioritizing chemicals screened as PMT represents an important exercise, since the results of the prioritization can help direct limited resources to focus on high-priority PMT chemicals, the results from which can be used by decision-makers to help inform transparent, effective and efficient prevention and mitigation solutions. Here, we briefly summarize the criteria used for screening PMT chemicals, and introduce a risk-based prioritization framework that we suggest can help support the decision-making process, either in the form of introducing mitigation actions aimed at reducing exposure to high-priority PMT chemicals or towards addressing key uncertainties aligned with various data gaps that might affect the outcome of the PMT assessment of a chemical substance.

Background

There are numerous examples of frameworks that have been developed aimed at screening and prioritizing organic chemicals with respect to their potential to persist and bioaccumulate [13–17]. Chemicals that are identified as being persistent in the environment, for instance, have been linked with being sufficiently hazardous, based on the assumption that the continued use and environmental release of a persistent chemical will result in its (bio)accumulation in the environment, where it may eventually exceed a toxicological threshold of concern, even if the toxicity is currently unknown [18]. More recently, mobility has been included within the CLP as a hazard criteria [8], which when combined with persistence, can potentially represent a risk to human health via exposure to contaminated drinking water.

With a specific emphasis on screening and prioritizing PMT/vPvM chemicals, Arp et al. [19], identified 172 unique chemical structures (belonging to 259 registered substances) that they characterized as High-Priority Category A. The High-Priority Category A list of chemicals represent substances that meet the screening criteria as PMT/vPvM and which are registered under REACH with registration volumes > 10 t/y, and are not currently subject to EU regulations [19]. The complete list of chemicals, which is an update to a 2019 UBA list of PMT/vPvM chemicals [20], includes a total of 343 unique chemical structures (belonging to 474 registered substances) that are identified as meeting the PMT/vPvM criteria. The remaining chemicals are assigned into one of two alternative categories, specifically as Moderate-Priority Category B (142 unique chemicals) based on registration volumes that are > 1 t/y and < 10 t/y, and a final Moderate-Priority Category C (29 unique chemicals), which are substances that are already subject to EU regulations [19]. Publication of the priority list of PMT/vPvM substances is presented by Arp et al. [19] as an incentive to registrants and downstream users of the chemicals to reduce and minimize emissions throughout the whole life cycle of their manufacture and use, and to also encourage the generation of more reliable and robust data pertaining to the criteria for persistence and mobility.

Considering that the High-Priority Category A list of PMT/vPvM substances represents high tonnage chemicals registered under REACH (i.e. > 10 t/y), there is a potential expectation that the data for these chemicals will be more robust than for the Moderate-Priority Category B list of substances. As an illustrative example, therefore, aimed at articulating the potential challenges associated with screening chemicals and the role that prioritization can play in helping to further support all stakeholders towards ensuring the safe and sustainable use of chemicals in commerce, we provide

a brief overview of the screening criteria and data used to assess the High-Priority Category A substances as potentially PMT/vPvM.

Persistence

In the EU, chemicals with a half-life > 40 days in fresh or estuarine water at 9 °C and pH 4–9 are considered to be persistent (P), and with a half-life > 60 days to be very persistent (vP). Alternatively, chemicals with half-lives > 120 d in either soil or fresh or estuarine sediment at 12 °C and pH 4–9 are also considered P, and with half-lives > 180 days vP. Because these criteria are already used to assess persistence of chemicals under REACH, it is thus reasonable that they should also be used to screen the persistency of chemicals that may also be mobile [1].

It is important to acknowledge, however, that concerns have been raised when considering the availability, reliability and relevance of quantitative data that might be used to evaluate the environmental persistence for candidate PMT/vPvM chemicals [21, 22]. For instance, the regulatory threshold values that are currently used are understood to have been defined based on our accumulated knowledge of the environmental fate and behaviour of a set of neutral non-polar hydrophobic organic chemicals, typical of PBT/vPvB chemicals [17, 23–26]. However, there are a large number of chemicals currently used in commerce, many of which are polar or ionizable organics [27], and for which there is limited to no experimental data of a media-specific half-life, such as in water, soils and/or sediment. Given that the properties of chemicals that may potentially meet the criteria as either PMT or vPvM include polar and ionizable organic chemicals, the limited availability of persistence data represents an important data need [21, 22, 28].

The assessment of persistence, for instance, presented by Arp et al. adopts a weight-of-evidence approach, using available data and read-across methods, which is applied to >60% of chemicals identified as either P or vP on the High-Priority Category A list, whereas only about 15% of those chemicals are reported to have measured degradation rate data [19]. The absence of measured half-life data for a wide range of chemicals is thus identified as an important data need, whereby prioritization can help inform which chemicals screened as being potentially P or vP should be given high priority with respect to strengthening their overall persistence data, such as by conducting appropriate experimental tests [19, 21, 22]. Below, we propose the adoption of a tiered risk-based prioritization framework, which we suggest is complementary to the screening-level prioritization approach presented by Arp et al. [19].

Mobility

Chemicals with properties that may result in their characterization as either PBT or vPvB, are typically characterized as hydrophobic organic chemicals. Under REACH, the screening threshold for bioaccumulation is defined for chemicals based on an assessment of their octanol–water partition coefficient (K_{OW}), whereby chemicals with $\log K_{OW} > 4.5$ have the potential to be prioritized as bioaccumulative [29]. Mobility, conversely, targets hydrophilic chemicals, which are unlikely to sorb efficiently to any solid substrate and, if a chemical is sufficiently persistent, thus has the potential to represent a persistent route of exposure to drinking water sources, depending on its emission to the environment. The current proposal for characterizing the mobility potential of a chemical is to screen and prioritize chemicals against their organic carbon–water partition constant (K_{OC}), whereby chemicals having a $\log K_{OC} < 3.0$ being mobile (M) and where $\log K_{OC} < 2.0$ would be very mobile (vM) [21].

Since many PMT chemicals are likely to be ionizable organic chemicals, it can be difficult to assess the sorption behaviour of the charged species of organic acids and bases, whereby different mechanisms of sorption between the ionized form of the chemical and system-dependent properties of the soil substrate can introduce significant differences in sorption behaviour that are not fully accounted for by K_{OC} [30, 31]. Caution is thus warranted when interpreting screening data based on estimates of K_{OC} , particularly when applying estimation methods that have been developed largely for neutral organic chemicals [22, 30–32]. Given the possible challenges that may arise in the instance of ionizable organic chemicals, a simplifying approach has been recommended, whereby the K_{OW} for ionizable organics is corrected by estimating a D_{OW} value, which is an adjusted form of K_{OW} according to a chemicals acid dissociation constant (pK_a) and system pH [19]. In this instance, the use of D_{OW} has been proposed as an additional metric to screen ionizable organic chemicals with respect to their mobility [33], whereby the lowest pH-dependent $\log D_{OW}$ over the pH range of 4–9 is < 4.5 is used as a screening threshold [1]. For example, approximately 40% of the 172 High-Priority Category A PMT/vPvM chemicals identified by Arp et al. [19], have been prioritized based on their estimated D_{OW} values. Similar to the challenges encountered with the limited amount of measured half-life data, the limited availability of measured K_{OC} data, along with the application of simplifying assumptions that are used for screening purposes, can result in a large screening list of chemicals meeting the mobility criteria. Prioritization, therefore represents an important part of the overall process, which can help inform which chemicals should be given high priority with respect to

reducing uncertainties regarding their potential mobility concerns [19, 21, 22].

Toxicity

In Europe, toxicity assessments include screening chemicals against a number of different toxicological endpoints including CMR (carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity), STOT-RE (specific target organ toxicity after repeated exposure), acute effects such as acute target organ toxicity after single exposure (STOT-SE), skin or eye irritation, freshwater ecotoxicity, and most recently endocrine disruption [8].

The recently published report of the European Environment Agency provides an overview on the testing and assessment status of chemicals in Europe [34]. There are approximately 100,000 synthetic chemicals on the market today [35], of which only a small subset of approximately 450 chemicals have a comprehensive toxicological data set covering most hazardous endpoints. From the remaining compounds, it is estimated that about 10,000 are relatively well characterized for most hazards, while 20,000 have modelled data and 70,000 are low-volume chemicals, having few to no data with respect to their toxicological properties.

When considering the 172 High-Priority Category A PMT/vPvM chemicals identified by Arp et al. [19], 47% meet the T-criteria based on data classifying them as CMR or STOT-RE. It is notable that 39% have no data, but have been classified as *potentially* toxic according to their screening as Cramer class III. Chemicals screened as potentially toxic based on their Cramer classification should be prioritized for refinement, since the Cramer classification does not provide a chemical-specific hazard assessment. Of the 172 chemicals, 10% is currently under assessment by regulatory agencies with respect to their toxicological hazard, whereby a broad consensus has not yet been reached regarding their toxicity. Consequently, caution is warranted due to the uncertainty surrounding their toxicity classification. Finally, 4% of the chemicals on the High-Priority Category A list do not include any toxicity data.

It is generally understood that the large number of data-poor chemicals requiring toxicity testing represents a challenge, in that the use of traditional animal studies to evaluate toxicity is characterized by a variety of concerns, including limited testing capacity, time to perform the studies, high cost and, and importantly, ethical concerns related to animal welfare. Recent and ongoing projects, such as PARC [36], ASPIS [37], RHT3R (<https://www.risk-hunt3r.eu/>), ToxCAST [38, 39] or APCRA [40], represent activities aimed at developing new toxicity testing strategies, such as defined approaches (DA) or integrated approaches to testing and assessment (IATAs), the

goal of which is to characterize the toxicity of chemicals using new approach methodologies (NAMs) consisting of in vitro test systems and in silico models. The scope of the specific testing required for an individual chemical or group of chemicals requires clarity with respect to the problem formulation, and intuitively differs for acute endpoints, such as skin irritation or sensitization, and systemic endpoints, such as chronic toxicity after repeated exposure. In the area of systemic toxicity, resulting from low level chronic exposure, a tiered testing strategy is foreseen. This strategy is built upon high-throughput in vitro testing that aims to provide a broad mechanistic coverage of various relevant toxicological endpoints, and then progresses to more complex test systems, for example, 3D or microfluidic systems, used to address alerts that may be identified from lower tiers of assessment.

Given the significant advances of NAMs and potential benefits, such as with respect to cost and time efficiency, as compared to most traditional in vivo studies, the ongoing development and application in chemical toxicity and risk assessment of NAMs is important, not only in the context of chemicals currently in use, but also to help strengthen the assessment of chemicals that may enter into commerce in the future [41]. For instance, there are several examples where chemicals regulated based on their P and B properties have been removed from the market, only to be replaced with equally harmful chemicals, resulting in regrettable substitution [42, 43]. Avoiding regrettable substitution would thus benefit from supporting advances in the development of NAMs and improved characterization of the toxicity of a chemical, which should be based on a mechanistic understanding as well as toxicokinetic properties to derive protective human health-based guidance values. In instances where toxicity data for similar compounds are available, NAMs can be used to support a read-across assessment [44, 45]. Indeed, there is evidence supporting a NAM-based toxicity assessment in the context of grouping or read-across [22, 44]. Toxicological hazard assessment of chemicals screened as being persistent and mobile through the application of NAMs, is therefore perceived as a prominent part of the risk-based prioritization framework presented below.

Risk-based prioritization

An important goal of the ZeroPM project is to develop and apply tools that could be used to prioritize chemicals that have the potential to be persistent and mobile, such as the 172 High-Priority Category A PMT/vPvM chemicals identified by Arp et al. [19]. While there are a variety of approaches that can be used for prioritization, and which are also explored within the ZeroPM project [22,

46, 47], here we present a risk-based prioritization framework that aims to characterize and quantify the toxicological hazards to human health that may result from exposure to PMT/vPvM chemicals via drinking water. Considering the numerous challenges surrounding the relevance and reliability associated with both the physicochemical and toxicity data that are available for the majority of chemicals used in commerce, and which are crucial for screening their potential to be PMT/vPvM, it is advisable to evaluate the influence of the relative uncertainty with respect to prioritization. We suggest that the assessment of uncertainty represents an essential part of the prioritization process, as it can provide valuable guidance towards the acquisition of pertinent and robust data that will help to reduce uncertainties identified for the most sensitive parameters, and thereby strengthen the overall decision-making process. An effective method to characterize and quantify the uncertainty, and to help guide the acquisition of additional data that might be used to effectively reduce uncertainties, is to consider the use of a tiered-assessment framework. Figure 1 provides an illustrative example, which summarizes commonly used strategies that have been adopted within a tiered risk assessment approach [48, 49].

The pyramid shown in Fig. 1 is meant to provide a generalized illustrative representation of a tiered-assessment process, and which is being adopted within ZeroPM. The base of the pyramid, for instance, represents a simplistic tier of assessment that uses a minimal amount of data. In the context of the ZeroPM project, this level of assessment represents the use

of available physicochemical property data to screen chemicals as possible persistent and mobile chemicals based on a comparison between their media-specific half-lives and log K_{OC} values against regulatory threshold criteria. Chemicals that exceed the criteria for persistence and mobility would then be screened for their potential to be toxic, which would also be based on an evaluation of available data and would likely include the use of various approaches, including TTC, QSAR and read-across. An example of a Tier 0 screening is the approach reported by Arp et al. [19], where they suggest that additional toxicity data (Tier 1) also considering long-term oral exposure (Tier 2) are required for chemicals screened as vPvM, as well as for the 421 substances in Annex A, which are considered persistent and mobile, but which lack high-quality consensus conclusions that the criteria for toxicity is met. Illustrating Tier 0 at the base of the pyramid, consequently, reflects the reality that a large number chemicals are likely to meet the screening criteria as PMT/vPvM (see also Chirsir et al. [22]), but that the data associated with this level of assessment is subject to high uncertainty, since the available data for the majority of chemicals are limited to non-existent. The primary objective of ZeroPM, therefore, is to develop and apply tools within Tier 1 that could address prioritization for chemicals screened as PMT/vPvM in Tier 0 (Fig. 1). The goal is to strengthen quantitative understanding with respect to both the toxicological hazard and human exposure to PMT/vPvM chemicals via drinking water, and thereby prioritize against the need for data

Fig. 1 Illustrative summary of ZeroPM tiered approach. The base of the pyramid (Tier 0) represents both the high number of chemicals and high level of uncertainty anticipated when screening chemicals with respect to their potential to be persistent and mobile. Moving from the screening Tier 0 level to the Tier 1 prioritization level aims at reducing both the number of chemicals and uncertainty, which will require a higher level of resource. Chemicals prioritized following Tier 1 can either move to high-tier assessment (Tier 2), which will involve significant resource and/or can already be prioritized for exposure mitigation measures

refinement aimed at reducing uncertainties or to prioritize for exposure reductions.

The overall approach presented here, thus represents a risk-based prioritization framework. Assuming that a base-level of information that might accompany a chemical registered under REACH is available, there is a high probability that a Tier 0 level of assessment, as reported by Arp et al. [19], will be associated with a high level of uncertainty. The purpose of a tiered risk assessment framework is to organize available data and to effectively communicate the rationale and need for additional testing at higher tiers, which can be adapted depending on the purpose of the assessment and the degree of uncertainty that is defined as acceptable. The type and degree of uncertainty at each tier in the assessment, however, needs to be characterized and communicated at a satisfactory level to ensure that the information obtained from the assessment is fit-for-purpose [50, 51]. The framework thus provides a level of transparency that can facilitate communication of results obtained from multiple lines of evidence.

Given the large numbers of chemicals for which there exists only a limited amount of data, the low tiers of assessment will require screening large numbers of chemicals, with the number of chemicals ideally decreasing with each progressive tier. The process, therefore, helps to prioritize chemicals based on conservative assumptions about their exposure and toxicological properties, while providing resources to acquire more robust data for high-priority chemicals.

An important component of the tiered approach illustrated in Fig. 1 is the connectivity between the exposure and toxicity assessment at each tier. Since the risk-based prioritization framework adopted here requires estimates of both exposure and the toxicity hazard, it seems logical that the overall approach should be integrated. Identifying which tier of assessment may initially be appropriate for a specific chemical depends on the relative availability of data for that chemical. Within a European context, the relative amount of data may be strongly influenced by the tonnage band of the chemical, which characterizes the amount of chemical manufactured and/or imported into the EU (Table S1). Specifically, as the tonnage band for a chemical increases, there is an associated increase in the amount of data required to support the registration of the chemical within the EU [7]. Here, we summarize key elements for each of the tiers illustrated in Fig. 1, including the respective types of information and uncertainties anticipated at each level of the assessment for chemicals screened as potential PMT/vPvM substances.

Exposure assessment

There are numerous challenges associated with estimating exposure. For example, it is relatively well understood that uncertainties associated with characterizing and quantifying emissions of chemicals used in commerce can represent the single largest source of uncertainty in predicting environmental concentrations (PECs) and/or estimating their environmental fate [52–54]. Concentrations of chemicals in the aquatic environment, obtained from either measured or modelling activities, can result in significant variability, influenced by differences related to the use and environmental release of the chemical or as a consequence of simplifying assumptions and/or limitations of the model used. Ideally, access to both model PECs and measured environmental concentrations (MECs) would represent a complementary source of information that should be used to refine the exposure assessment [55].

For potential PMT/vPvM chemicals, the properties of persistence and mobility, coupled with data regarding the total tonnage used, can be used as surrogates of exposure, representing a Tier 0 screening-level assessment [19]. Under the EU chemicals regulation, REACH, the tonnage of all chemicals used must be registered, with the standard information requirements aligned to each tonnage band (Table S1). For all chemicals manufactured and/or imported into the EU > 1 t/a there is a requirement to report the physicochemical properties of the chemical, including its water solubility, vapour pressure, K_{OW} , etc., along with estimates of degradation and/or results from biodegradation testing. The data defined represent the minimal level of information that can be used to enable an assessment of the potential for a chemical to meet the criteria of PMT/vPvM.

In the context of chemicals meeting the PMT/vPvM criteria, an important concern relates to human exposure via drinking water. Generally, sources of drinking water can be characterized as originating from either treated surface water or groundwater. Groundwater, in particular, represents an important drinking water source for nearly 50% of the global urban population [56]. Some groundwater bodies can be particularly vulnerable to chemical pollution, either from point sources (such as chemical spillages or leaching containment facilities) or from diffuse-source leaching of chemicals applied to land (e.g. in pesticides or biosolid applications). Chemicals in contaminated surface waters can also migrate into adjacent shallow groundwater, which can sometimes be abstracted for water supply (e.g. in bank filtration systems). Due to relatively slow flow rates and long recharge times, mitigating contaminated groundwater can face a variety of formidable challenges [57]. Stream beds and river banks, in particular, represent complex sub-surface

porous environments where groundwater interacts with surface water, exhibiting considerable environmental variability [56, 58–60]. Differences in soil types further influence aqueous permeability, while alterations in landscape and hydrology can modify the slope and depth of available groundwater. To model these interactions effectively, several relatively complex chemistry transfer models are available for site-specific assessments, estimating pollutant concentrations in bank filtrate [59–62], and which represent higher-tier (Tier 2) refinement tools.

In contrast, screening-level multimedia environmental fate and exposure models often rely on simplifying assumptions of the characteristics of soils and aquifers. These include representing soil compartments as well-mixed boxes and treating diffusion and advection processes as one-dimensional. The advantage of adopting simplifying assumptions is that pollutant exposure concentrations can be estimated with lower data and computational demands, such as those commonly used to evaluate pesticide leaching in regulatory approvals [63]. Simplified models are commonly used in regulatory assessments of general chemicals. In the EU, for instance, the European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances (EUSES) [55, 64] is the standard environmental exposure assessment tool used to calculate PECs within a generic regional model environment. EUSES, therefore, would represent the standard tool used to derive a Tier 1 PEC for chemicals screened as potential PMT/vPvM substances.

EUSES employs many simplifying assumptions for screening-level multimedia environmental fate and exposure estimations. In low tier ('screening') assessments such simplifying assumptions can be used to screen and prioritize chemicals, as long as these fall within the applicability domain of the model. Of course, if the organic chemicals being evaluated fall outside the applicability domain of a generic multimedia model, the accuracy and confidence in predicted environmental fate and transport decreases. For example, generalized assumptions pertaining to the interactions of chemicals, such as their partitioning and mobility in the environment, can be significantly influenced by assumptions about the depth and volume of environmental media (air, water, and soils) as well as to the various constituents found in each of these media, including the volume fractions of air, water and organic carbon content [65]. To characterize and quantify the relative influence of simplifying assumptions on the environmental fate and exposure of chemicals with varying physicochemical properties, a sensitivity and uncertainty analysis can be performed [65]. Insights gained from sensitivity and uncertainty analyses can help support a variety of activities, including model refinement and informing monitoring strategies, aimed

at strengthening the exposure assessment of chemicals [66–68].

Currently, there is a need to develop and apply models to assess the exposure of PMT/vPvM chemicals in drinking water [9, 69]. Existing multimedia environmental fate models, such as EUSES, describe soil and groundwater with a few layers, and with little or no consideration of unsaturated zone dispersion and no option to explore river to groundwater transport, which might take place in bank filtration scenarios [70]. In the EU Technical Guidance Document (TGD) [55], for instance, the pore water concentration in the (unsaturated) agricultural soil compartment (mixing depth of 0.2 m) is considered representative of the groundwater concentration. This simplistic assumption might be argued to be a worst-case scenario because highly sorptive chemicals have a low probability to leach to deeper soil layers and into groundwater. A potential limitation, however, is that this worst-case scenario argument may not be appropriate for chemicals with properties consistent with chemicals screened as PMT/vPvM, for which considerable leaching is presumed to occur. Our goal is to, thus, evaluate the applicability domain of this assumption by enhancing existing fugacity and activity-based approaches for a more accurate estimation of the fate and mobility of organic chemicals, with a focus on improving their description of groundwater–surface water interactions. Intuitively, an improved understanding of the fate and transport of chemical pollutants in the sub-surface environment can provide better support towards estimating their concentrations in groundwater. This is particularly important when models are used to assess human exposure to PMT/vPvM chemicals via drinking water. It is important to note that our proposed approach is not intended to replicate higher-tier (Tier 2) models such as those used in pesticide regulation [63] or in the remediation of site-specific contaminant plumes [71]. Instead, it is designed to offer a tool which is consistent with other generic (Tier 1) screening-level multimedia models used in regulatory chemical risk assessment, such as EUSES [55, 67, 68].

Our goal in ZeroPM is to enhance existing fugacity and activity-based approaches for a more accurate estimation of the fate and mobility of organic chemicals, with a focus on improving their description of groundwater–surface water interactions, based on models developed by Cousins et al. [72] and Sun et al. [73]. Intuitively, an improved understanding of the fate and transport of chemical pollutants in the sub-surface environment can provide better support towards estimating their concentrations in groundwater. Furthermore, the modelling approach adopted is based on the multimedia activity model developed by Franco and Trapp [74], which enables an

evaluation of the environmental fate and transport of ionizable organic chemicals, and thereby expands the applicability domain to consider the sub-surface mobility of organic chemicals that are likely to be more soluble in water. This is particularly important when models are used to assess human exposure to PMT/vPvM chemicals via drinking water. The proposed model, thus, provides potentially improved exposure estimates of PMT/vPvM chemicals in groundwater, compared to existing tools, such as EUSES, which do not include this capability.

The estimated concentrations in groundwater are used as worst-case surrogates for drinking water concentrations consumed by humans. These estimates are then used as input to a Tier 1 physiologically based kinetic (PBK) model, also called forward dosimetry, to enable an internal human exposure to be estimated. The development and application of the PBK model will thus enable the extrapolation of PEC_{DW} into bioavailable internal concentrations of PMT/vPvM substances for humans, which can later be compared to in vitro-derived toxicological benchmark concentrations (see below). Dependence on the mode of action of the modelled compound, this human equivalent concentration after single or repeated exposure is determined for human plasma or for a specific tissue that is most relevant for risk assessment. As outlined in the recently published guidance by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2022), the uncertainty of the PBK modelling needs to be addressed, e.g. by comparing the modelled ADME (adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion) to in vivo ADME data. However, in vivo ADME data are typically lacking for some groups of chemicals, such as those identified as potential PMT/vPvM candidates. To address this need, ZeroPM proposes an assessment framework that can be used to characterize and validate PBK models using compound specific ADME data, utilizing new approach methodologies (NAMs). Major sources of uncertainties are outlined with regard to model assumptions, input data, as well as results.

Because many of the chemicals screened for their potential to be PMT/vPvM have been detected in the environment (see for instance [75–80]), it is also reasonable to consider a Tier 2 exposure assessment. A Tier 2 assessment utilizes MECs, and would thus aim to compile environmental monitoring data in surface and/or groundwater, as well as in drinking water, to represent an external exposure concentration for human exposure. Intuitively, the availability of MECs would also serve as a valuable resource to evaluate the performance of multimedia models to estimate PEC_{DW} . At Tier 2, the environmental monitoring data would thus be used as input to the PBK model, to estimate a human internal

concentration. Alternatively, human biomonitoring data could be compiled to evaluate the concentrations of PMT/vPvM chemicals within a given population as input to a risk assessment. In the case of monitoring data it will be important to characterize the variability that may likely occur. Variance in monitoring data can result for a variety of reasons. For example, monitoring data often reflect snapshots in space and time with respect to the detection of a chemical contaminant in surface or groundwater, as well as within human populations such as might be obtained from biomonitoring data. In these instances, therefore, transparency regarding the variability, as well as the reliability of the data generated needs to be considered. See for instance the recent approach proposed to enable an assessment of the various criteria for reporting and evaluating exposure datasets (CREED) used in environmental exposure assessments [81–84].

Toxicity assessment

In parallel, and integrated with the exposure assessment, is the need to derive appropriate estimates of toxicity for chemicals identified as possible PMT/vPvM candidates. For instance, initial estimates of toxicity may influence the approach taken towards estimating exposure, such as helping to guide resources aimed at collecting physico-chemical property and emissions data, as well as model scenario development. If a chemical is shown to have a very low toxicity, it is possible that lower-tier, conservative exposure estimates may provide a sufficient level of precision that is fit-for-purpose. Conversely, early indications of high toxicity suggest a greater need for data refinement, supported by accurate estimates of uncertainty regarding human exposure.

Tier 0 applies in silico approaches (like QSARs or TTC) or existing data (e.g. read-across) for the hazard characterization of potential PMT/vPvM compounds. QSAR models are available for different types of toxicological endpoints, such as mutagenicity or sensitization. However, it can be noted that QSAR models are not available to estimate the systemic toxicity of compounds after repeated exposure. On the other hand, guidance is available with respect to assessing and combining rule-based or statistical QSAR models, such as expert judgement to come to a conclusion (e.g. ICHM7 guideline on genotoxic impurities [85]). The applicability of a QSAR approach, i.e. its relevance and predictivity for a given toxicological endpoint and its applicability to the compound in question, must be assessed before its use. The concept of the threshold of toxicological concern (TTC) provides a general threshold based on the structural properties of compounds below which chronic oral exposure is not expected to have any health effects on humans. As TTC does not characterize the toxicological potency/hazard of

a compound, it is often used as screening tool to regulate low level exposure of e.g. impurities in drugs/food [86, 87]. Read-across or grouping approaches are also integrated into Tier 0, as they use existing endpoint data from similar “source” compounds to predict the toxicological properties of an unknown target compound [88]. Structural similarity is often used as a starting point to identify source compounds. A closer evaluation of shared toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic properties is subsequently performed to assure that the grouped compounds are also similar with regard to their toxicological properties. Within the assessment of shared toxicological properties, targeted testing using NAM approaches, based on a read-across hypothesis can help to reduce the uncertainty in the read-across prediction [44].

In Tier 1, *in vitro* screening models are used to support prioritization and screening. As outlined above the scope of the *in vitro* testing battery depends on the problem formulation. For instance, a battery of specific *in vitro* bioassays can be used to screen for modes of action and to derive *in vitro* benchmark concentrations (BMC) from dose–response relationships, which can be used as a protective point of departure. For this purpose, simple assays are often applied, which use isolated macromolecules (DNA, RNA, proteins) or single cell types (e.g. reporter gene assays). Results from such assays can also be used to generate a hypothesis on a mechanism of action, which can then be further investigated in more complex NAMs with higher physiological relevance because they may consider metabolic capacity, structure (e.g. 3D, organelles) or a combination of both (e.g. organ on chip technologies, zebrafish embryos, nematodes).

Within the ZeroPM project, a combination of NAMs is performed to screen the *in vitro* toxicity of a selected set of PMT/vPvM compounds belonging to three different chemical classes, which include triazoles, triazines, and perfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS) [89]. The aim of this screening is to provide a proof-of-principle that NAM-derived BMCs (as part of Tier 1) can be used for prioritization purposes. Typically, *in vitro* derived BMCs are based on nominal concentrations, and don't reflect the actual concentration to which the cells in the bioassays are exposed. To account for typical processes that might alter the nominal concentration of a chemical in an *in vitro* bioassay, such as evaporation, protein and plastic binding as well as the ability of the compounds to partition into the tested cell model, *in vitro* biokinetic modelling approaches are used to calculate the effective *in vitro* concentration as recently reviewed by Proenca et al. [90]. PBK modelling is then used for the *in vitro*-to-*in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE), which provides a human equivalent benchmark concentration in plasma or tissues. The internal benchmark concentration is subsequently

compared to the bioavailable internal exposure concentration that is derived by forward PBK dosimetry. This results in a risk-based prioritization of PMT/vPvM chemicals that can be used to support the regulatory decision-making process, with a specific focus on prevention of further emission and exposure.

In current REACH and CLP legislation, however, NAMs are only accepted for hazard identification and classification of skin sensitizers [91], while hazard characterization is highly dependent on the use of *in vivo* toxicity data. Therefore, Tier 2 comprises traditional *in vivo* toxicity data, which is obtained from animal testing and epidemiological studies. Given the emphasis of the ZeroPM project towards demonstrating a proof-of-principle prioritization framework, conducting a higher level of assessment (Tier 2) is beyond the scope of the project. Nevertheless, *in vivo* toxicity data will be considered within ZeroPM, as far as this information is already available (i.e. data-rich compounds), and represents an important source of data to substantiate the proof-of-principle that a NAM-based approach can be used for prioritization purposes leading to similar conclusions as an *in vivo* approach.

Proof-of-principle case study

A proof-of-principle case study is proposed as part of ZeroPM to demonstrate how a battery of *in vitro* bioassays can be used, in combination with estimates of human exposure, for prioritization purposes. The case study has a focus on three classes of compounds, including many representative compounds that have properties consistent with the PMT/vPvM criteria. The ZEROPM-BOX1 list of chemicals, for instance, contains 36 chemicals, that specifically include triazoles, triazines, and PFAS [89]. All three classes contain data-rich compounds, for which *in vivo* and epidemiological (Tier 2) toxicity data are available. For these compounds, the predictive value of the NAM-based *in vitro* hazard characterization followed by the IVIVE approach can thus be validated using the available *in vivo* toxicity data. Based on the results obtained, it is proposed that similar *in vitro* hazard characterization, followed by IVIVE modelling will be performed for data-poor compounds, for which *in vivo* data are scarce. To support the proof-of-principle approach, we thus propose to test all chemicals for their ability to affect one of four endpoints (summarized below), for which representatives of at least one of the three compound classes are known to cause an *in vivo* response.

1. Estrogen, androgen, thyroid and steroidogenesis (EATS): Triazoles and triazines are well-known disruptors of the steroidogenesis [92], while PFAS are considered to be thyroid hormone system disruptors.

tors [93]. In addition, some studies report effects of triazoles on the estrogen and androgen receptor [94]. Therefore, all compounds are tested for their estrogen, androgen, thyroid, and steroidogenesis (EATS) modalities by determining their agonistic and antagonistic capacity towards the estrogen, androgen, and thyroid receptor (ER, AR, TR) in reporter gene assays. In addition, their capacity to displace thyroid hormone from its distributor protein transthyretin (TTR) is determined. Finally, disruption of steroidogenesis is studied by analysis of 13 steroid hormones, including testosterone and 17 β -estradiol, in human adeno-carcinoma H295R cells exposed to the test compounds. The screening of EATS modalities has been finalized and published by Carlier et al. [95].

2. Developmental (neuro)toxicity: Because all three classes of compounds contain developmental toxicants [96–101], the test compounds are screened in zebrafish embryotoxicity assays. First, concentration-dependent effects on zebrafish embryo morphology and heartbeat are determined. Next, additional experiments are performed to screen for neurodevelopmental effects, by measuring behavioural changes in embryos exposed to concentrations that do not cause malformations or changes in heartbeat.
3. Immunotoxicity: In Europe, the effects of PFAS on the immune system are considered as most critical for regulation of PFAS in food [102]. Therefore, the immunotoxicity of the test compounds is determined in zebrafish embryos injected with fluorescent *Mycobacterium marinum* bacteria.

In a previous risk assessment [103], effects on liver or levels high-density cholesterol (HDL) in serum, which is highly dependent on liver metabolism, were considered to be the most critical effects for PFOA and PFOS, respectively. Therefore, cell functioning, mitochondrial activity, oxidative stress, and lipid accumulation is studied in the HepaRG liver cell line after exposure to the test compounds. Additionally, triazoles also show predominantly liver effects in repeat-dose mammalian in vivo studies, with effects, such as steatosis and necrosis, typically being observed, with the liver toxicity of triazoles mediated by nuclear receptor activation [104]. Therefore, cell functioning, mitochondrial activity, oxidative stress, and lipid accumulation is studied in the HepaRG liver cell line after exposure to the test compounds.

Application of a risk matrix communication tool

The objective within the ZeroPM project is to evaluate the relative effectiveness of the risk-based prioritization framework proposed to prioritize candidate PMT/vPvM chemicals for additional data acquisition or towards

identifying solutions aimed at preventing exposure. To simplify the communication of the output that might be obtained from both the toxicity and exposure assessment, we apply the Risk21 matrix [49]. Here we present several hypothetical scenarios as illustrative examples of what we might anticipate as output from the overall proposed risk-based prioritization framework.

We could consider, for example, a suite of hypothetical chemicals identified as possible persistent and mobile contaminants, and how they might be represented in the prioritization matrix. Figure 2 presents several different possible results regarding how a group of chemicals might be plotted within the prioritization matrix. Since the objective of the risk-based prioritization framework proposed within ZeroPM is to identify high-priority PMT/vPvM chemicals, intuitively, chemicals associated with both relatively high toxicity and high exposure will be assigned the highest priority. For this group of chemicals (illustrated in the upper right-hand corner of Fig. 2), it is reasonable to anticipate regulatory actions should be implemented, aimed at reducing and/or eliminating the

Fig. 2 Hypothetical illustrative example of various outputs that might be visualized using the risk-based prioritization matrix. Chemicals that fall in the upper right hand corner of the matrix should be assigned high priority, conversely chemicals in the lower left hand corner imply low priority. There may, however, also be instances where chemicals have relatively high toxicity but low exposure (upper left-hand corner), or have relatively high exposure but low toxicity (lower right-hand corner), both of which warrant moderate priority. Decisions on how to prioritize chemicals that fall within these regions may require additional data aimed at refining either exposure or toxicity. Lastly, it is possible that chemicals may be associated with relatively large uncertainties with respect to their toxicity and/or exposure. In these instances, refinement for either toxicity or exposure, or both may be necessary

use of these chemicals in commerce. Conversely, chemicals identified as meeting the persistence and mobility criteria, but have relatively low toxicity and exposure, should be assigned a lower priority with respect to implementing regulatory actions, but may still require additional data aimed at refining either the exposure and/or toxicity assessment.

For chemicals that fall in the upper left-hand corner of Fig. 2 (i.e. high toxicity/low exposure) it may be necessary to obtain data aimed at refining their exposure assessment, influenced by the relative uncertainty that surrounds the exposure, such as the accuracy regarding what is known with respect to environmental release and fate of the chemical that may result in unattended human exposure, assuming that this information may be incomplete at a Tier 1 level of assessment. It is suggested that this group of chemicals should be given moderate priority, with similar priority being assigned to chemicals observed to have a relatively high exposure, but which have low toxicity (i.e. lower right-hand corner of Fig. 2). Consequently, it may be beneficial for chemicals that are screened as potentially meeting the persistence and mobility criteria, and are observed to have moderate priority, to obtain an improved understanding of their environmental fate, such as by obtaining more robust data with respect to their environmental half-lives and sorption behaviour. This is suggested based on observations made above regarding the limited number of chemicals for which robust degradation and mobility data are available. Therefore, for chemicals that might fall in either the upper left- or lower right-hand corner of the prioritization matrix, we recommend a need to strengthen the overall exposure assessment, such as with respect to their persistence and mobility and/or an improved understanding of their environmental release.

Lastly, we anticipate that there are likely to be instances where chemicals have a relatively large uncertainty with respect to either their toxicity or exposure estimates, as illustrated in the central part of Fig. 2. In these instances, relatively high uncertainties may be observed for both the toxicity and the exposure, or may be limited to either the toxicity or exposure assessment. Identifying the specifics regarding which factors drive the relative uncertainties with respect to either toxicity and/or exposure is fundamental towards helping to guide the acquisition of additional data that can be used to reduce the relative uncertainties and help to better understand how to best prioritize the chemical in question.

While the hypothetical illustrative examples shown in Fig. 2 are presented to provide a broad conceptual understanding of how the prioritization matrix might be applied, we present an illustrative example of a risk-based prioritization matrix for four well-studied

chemicals that have been screened as persistent and mobile contaminants (i.e. PFOA, PFOS, atrazine and melamine). Currently, there are several regulatory bodies have evaluated the toxicological hazard for chemicals included in the ZEROPM list of 36 chemicals, which include perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS), atrazine and melamine. Table 1 summarizes the toxicological values that have been derived for these four chemicals by various regulatory bodies, as well as a summary of concentrations in surface waters reported for each of the four chemicals, retrieved from the NORMAN EMPODAT database [105]. The dataset presented in Table 1 can be used to illustrate the interpretation of a realistic prioritization matrix (Fig. 3). It should be noted that in this example toxicity and exposure estimates are compared at the dose level, i.e. critical doses derived from animal studies and are compared to exposures through drinking water derived from reported surface water concentrations. In the ultimate ZeroPM prioritization matrices, however toxicity and exposure estimates will be compared as human equivalent concentrations in plasma or tissues, derived by extrapolating NAM-based BMCs using IVIVE modelling and drinking water exposure concentrations by forward dosimetry modelling.

From Fig. 3a it can be seen that estimates of exposure for both PFOS and PFOA, which are based on the maximum concentrations detected in surface water in the NORMAN EMPDAT database, would imply high priority for these chemicals, given that exposure concentrations are observed to exceed recommended daily intake values. This observation is consistent with the current concerns that have been raised regarding exposure to both PFOS and PFOA. We note, however, that estimates of exposure and regulatory toxicity values, are both associated with >4 orders of magnitude variability, which results in considerable uncertainty. When considering the distribution of measured concentrations reported for PFOS and PFOA in surface water it is notable that the median concentration is below the limit of detection, with the distribution being skewed by a small number of relatively high concentrations. These results would imply that the majority of exposure via surface water to PFOS and PFOA, may therefore be below a level of concern. Consequently, it is important to provide continuing support towards monitoring human exposure to PFOS and PFOA to ensure that exposure remains below toxicological levels of concern. Similarly, given the wide range of toxicity values summarized in Table 1 for PFOS and PFOA, it is recommended that additional priority measures target working towards a consensus regarding what might best represent an acceptable conservative threshold value [109].

Table 1 Summary of toxicological values and chemical occurrence data obtained from the NORMAN EMPODAT database [105] for four well-studied chemicals included in the proof-of-principle strategy presented

Chemical	Toxicological regulatory points of departure for human health			Exposure (environmental concentrations)			
	Regulatory body	Toxicological reference value	Toxicological endpoint	Maximum (µg/L)	Median (µg/L)	Number of measurements	Estimated exposure (µg/kg/day) ^h
Atrazine	EPA ^a	RfD: 0.0015 mg/kg/day [106]	Reproductive and developmental effects	0.054 ^a	0.003 ^a	41 ^a	0.0018
	EPA	MCL: 3 µg/L in drinking water [106]	Chronic exposure risks (reproduction)				
	EFSA ^b	ADI: 0.002 mg/kg/day ^b	Developmental and endocrine effects				
Melamine	FDA ^c	TDI: 0.63 mg/kg/day [107]	Kidney toxicity (Kidney stones)	19	0.66	1847	0.63
	WHO ^d /EFSA	TDI: 0.2 mg/kg/day [107]	Renal damage and toxicity				
PFOA	FSANZ ^e	0.02 µg/kg/day [108]	Developmental toxicity and liver toxicity	124	LOD ^g	67,339	4.1
	WHO EFSA ^f	0.1 µg/L [109] ADI: 0.63 ng/kg/day [110]	Immunotoxicity Liver and developmental toxicity				
PFOS	FSANZ	0.02 µg/kg/day [108]	Liver toxicity, immunotoxicity and developmental	17.1	LOD ^g	52,054	0.57
	WHO EFSA	0.1 µg/L [109] ADI: 0.63 ng/kg/day [110]	Immunotoxicity Liver and developmental toxicity				

RfD is chronic reference dose, MCL is maximum contaminant level, ADI is accepted daily intake, and TDI is tolerable daily intake

^a United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) (<https://www.cdc.gov/TSP/ToxProfiles/ToxProfiles.aspx?id=338&tid=59>)

^b European Food Standards Agency (EFSA) value based on information presented by the European Environment Agency (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/pesticides-in-rivers-lakes-and?activeAccordion=546a7c35-9188-4d23-94ee-005d97c26f2b>)

^c United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA)

^d World Health Organization

^e Food Standards Australia and New Zealand (FSANZ)

^f European Food Safety Authority

Results summarized for groundwater, as no concentrations above the LOD reported in surface waters

^g Most frequently reported lowest Limit of Detection (LOD) = 0.0007 µg/L

^h Estimated exposure based on assuming 2L of drinking water consumed per day and an average human weight of 60 kg

In the instance of both atrazine and melamine, on the other hand, the relative uncertainties with respect to their toxicity and exposure suggest lower prioritization than for PFOS and PFOA, based on their positioning within Fig. 3. For atrazine, environmental concentrations reported in groundwater samples are observed to have less variability than for the other environmental contaminants, whereas there are a range of toxicological values that have been adopted by different regulatory agencies. In the European Union, atrazine

is banned for use, which may partially explain the low variability in MECs, however, there have been observations of concentrations in bank-filtrate water being higher than in surface waters [111]. Given that the relative toxicity of atrazine is observed to be several orders of magnitude greater than for melamine, it does appear beneficial to continue to monitor levels of atrazine in the environment, particularly in groundwater, and to ensure that exposure levels remain below potential safety concerns.

Fig. 3 Prioritization matrix for PFOS, PFOA, atrazine and melamine, based on the data presented in Table 1

Similar to PFOS and PFOA, the environmental concentrations of melamine in surface water are observed to have significant variability, ranging over three orders of magnitude, consistent with data reported by Lütjens et al. [112]. Unlike PFOS and PFOA, however, the distribution of concentrations is not as highly skewed, whereby the mean and median values are observed to be similar to each other, being 0.91 and 0.66 $\mu\text{g/L}$, respectively. While the tonnages of PFOS, PFOA and atrazine are < 10 t/y, the tonnage of melamine is > 10 t/y. A major use of melamine in commerce is as melamine formaldehyde resin, which is added to tableware. While data are available that suggest the potential for melamine to leach from melamine resin products, the emission rates are considered to be potentially low [112]. Alternatively, there are also several other mechanisms by which melamine may be released to the environment, which include via the degradation of cyromazine, releases from the use of cyanamide-containing fertilizers and from the degradation of encapsulated fragrances [112]. The different use-scenarios may therefore represent important factors to consider regarding how the use and release of melamine may influence MECs. When combining the available toxicity and exposure data, which results in melamine falling within the lower left-hand corner of Fig. 3, it thus seems reasonable to suggest a low-to-moderate priority, whereby data aimed at better understanding the environmental releases of melamine would likely help provide insight regarding how to best target actions related to the key sources of exposure to melamine in drinking water.

Identifying the major sources of melamine to the environment would thus help support effective and efficient decision-making aimed at minimizing human exposure.

Conclusions

An important element of the ZeroPM project is to demonstrate that all chemicals, including those identified as PMT/vPvM, can be prioritized for the decision-making process based on a robust and reliable risk-based analysis. The risk-based prioritization is performed at a Tier 1 level, making use of either modelled worst-case drinking water concentrations, or where available MECs, that are used to calculate a human internal exposure concentration by PBK modelling and effect-based benchmark concentrations derived by NAMs using in vitro effect-concentrations and quantitative in vitro–in vivo extrapolation (i.e. Q-IVIVE) modelling. Within the ZeroPM project, the proof-of-principle for this approach will be obtained using data-rich compounds, with relatively low uncertainty in exposure, toxicokinetic, and toxicodynamic knowledge. A challenge will be to apply this approach to more data-poor candidate PMT/vPvM compounds in a later stage. We suggest that the approach presented here provides a valuable framework that can be developed by all stakeholders, which can also include helping to support prioritization activities for specific contaminated sites or for addressing priority-setting with respect to ambient exposure to potential PMT/vPvM chemicals.

Abbreviations

ADME	Adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion
BMC	Benchmark concentration
CLP	Classification, labelling and packaging
CMR	Carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity
D_{ow}	PH-corrected octanol–water partition coefficient
EATS	Estrogen, androgen, thyroid, and steroidogenesis
EUSES	European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances
IVIVE	In vitro-to-in vivo extrapolation
K_{oc}	Organic carbon–water partition coefficient
K_{ow}	Octanol–water partition coefficient
PBK	Physiologically based kinetic model
PBT	Persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic
PEC	Predicted environmental exposure
pK_a	Logarithm of the acid dissociation constant
MEC	Measured environmental concentration
NAMs	New approach methodologies
PMT/vPvM	Persistent, Mobile and Toxic/very Persistent and very Mobile
QSAR	Quantitative structure activity relationship
STOT-RE	Specific target organ toxicity after repeat exposure
STOT-SE	Specific target organ toxicity, skin or eye irritation
SVHC	Substances of very high concern
TGD	EU Technical Guidance Document
TTC	Threshold of toxicological concern
vPvB	Very Persistent/very Bioaccumulative

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